

THRESHOLDS

Adriana Sa

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Biographical information

With a background in music and visual arts, Adriana Sa has been investigating upon the reciprocal contamination of creative means and sensibilities. Trans-disciplinary artist, performer improviser/ composer, she (re)creates her instrumentation to pursue physical relations between light, music, space, weather, movement, time and people.

Adriana has been developing and presenting her work around Europe, USA and Japan; venues include Serralves Museum, Gulbenkian Foundation, Chiado Museum, Luzboa Biennale, Experimental Intermedia Foundation, PS1, Arteleku, Caixa Forum, Metronom, TUBE, AA-Architectural association, Digital Research Unit Huddersfield, ICA, Sonic Arts Research Center, Aomori Contemporary Art Center and STEIM amongst many others.

Description of Piece

'THRESHOLDS' is structured by the SOUNDING LIGHT INSTRUMENT (light sensors, i-cube, Lisa software), which translates light gradients into sound variations. It (re)establishes relationships between the site and its environmental context.

Natural and artificial light as well as body shadow affect sound behaviour in real-time according to the previous programming. Sound-source materials relate to personal site-specific memories and perceptions. Soundscape builds upon loops of previously prepared samples, whose transformations depend on the sensors' physical set-up and mapping. Their resulting mix is unrepeatably as the day unfolds. The inconstant behaviour of light must be framed during the site-specific work process.

The set-up offers different performative possibilities. Along the day, people are shown an orchestra of slow daylight changes playing within massive sound density; the site is here maestro. When it is dark outside, the installation invites for interacting on the soundscape; shadows play upon the sound-pictured city. By twilight, both sorts of playfulness overlap while soundscape features its peak behaviors.

The poetic logics underlying this work play with subtle shapes. Technical components like cables also assume the value of physical raw-material while drawing themselves volumetrically in space.

